

Supplementary material

Enhancing Resilience: the Impact of Flood Hazard and Vulnerability on Business Interruption Losses

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DRAFT

What is the total damage to **the company building** (excluding contents, etc.), estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)	
999	I don't know
998	Not applicable

Ask only if Q024 - B3_2,4	
Q249 - B3_6_2:	Numeric

What is the total damage to the **floor**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)	
999	I don't know
998	Not applicable

Ask only if Q024 - B3_2,9	
Q250 - B3_6_3:	Numeric

What is the total damage to **the inventory**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)	
999	I don't know
998	Not applicable

Ask only if Q024 - B3_2,8	
Q251 - B3_6_4:	Numeric

What is the total damage to **machines and equipment**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)	
999	I don't know
998	Not applicable

Ask only if **Q024 - B3_2,10**

Q252 - B3_6_5:

Numeric

What is the total damage to the company's **car and/or motorcycle**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)

999 I don't know
998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q024 - B3_2,7**

Q253 - B3_6_6:

Numeric

What is the total damage caused by **cleaning costs**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)

999 I don't know
998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q024 - B3_2,11**

Q254 - B3_6_7:

Numeric

What is the total damage caused by **looting and burglary**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)

999 I don't know
998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q024 - B3_2,996**

Q255 - B3_6_8:

Numeric

What is the total damage to **other possessions**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)

999 I don't know
998 Not applicable

Q256 - B3_6_9_1:

Numeric

And how high is the **total damage**, estimated by yourself?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)

- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if NOT **Q256 - B3_6_9_1** <= 2000000

Q293 - B3_6_9_2:

Single coded

Can you estimate the **total damage to the company** (excluding contents, etc.)?

- 1 Less than 1.000 euro
- 2 Between 1.000 and 5.000 euro
- 3 Between 5.000 and 10.000 euro
- 4 Between 10.000 and 50.000 euro
- 5 Between 50.000 and 100.000 euro
- 6 More than 100.000 euro
- 999 I don't know

Ask only if **Q029 - B3_7,1**

Q031 - B3_9_1:

Multi coded

Can you indicate for each source how much compensation you have already received and how much compensation you expect?

Your answers will not be used by governments or insurers to determine reimbursements.

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from the **home insurance**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q029 - B3_7,2**

Q032 - B3_9_2:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from the **content insurance**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q029 - B3_7,3**

Q033 - B3_9_3:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from the **business interruption insurance**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q029 - B3_7,4,5**

Q034 - B3_9_4:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from the **car insurance**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Q035 - B3_9_5:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from **the government** (Disaster Compensation Act)?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Q036 - B3_9_6:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from the **disaster fund**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q029 - B3_7,6**

Q037 - B3_9_7:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from **technical insurances** (For example, machinery breakdown, construction allrisk)?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q029 - B3_7,7**

Q038 - B3_9_8:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from the **transport insurance**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Q039 - B3_9_9:

Multi coded

How much compensation have you already received and/or do you still expect from **another source**?

If you don't expect any compensation from this source, enter 0.

- 1 Compensation you have already received (in €):
- 2 Compensation you expect to receive (in €):
- 999 I don't know
- 998 Not applicable

Ask only if **Q039 - B3_9_9,1,2,999**

Q040 - B3_10:

Open

Can you clarify what you mean by "another source" in the previous question?

Q294 - B3_11_1:

Numeric

How much **total** compensation do you expect for the damage you have incurred?

If you are unsure of the total fee, please estimate (in euros)

- 999 I don't know

Ask only if NOT Q294 - B3_11_1 <= 2000000

Q041 - B3_11_2:

Single coded

Can you still estimate how much you expect in total compensation for the damage you have incurred?

- 1 Less than €5.000
- 2 Between €5.000 and €9.999
- 3 Between €10.000 and €24.999
- 4 Between €25.000 and €49.999
- 5 Between €50.000 and €99.999
- 6 Between €100.000 and €249.999
- 7 Between €250.000 and €499.999
- 8 Between €500.000 and €999.999
- 9 €1.000.000 or more
- 999 I don't know

Has the water caused the following types of pollution to company property?

Multiple answers are possible.

- 1 No pollution
- 2 Oil or petrol
- 3 Chemicals
- 4 Sewage or stool
- 5 Mud
- 6 Waster
- 996 Other materials, ...
- 999 I don't know

Q045 - B4_2:

Numeric

Approximately what percentage of your suppliers were located within a radius of 10 km before the flood?

- 999 I don't know
- 997 Not applicable

Q046 - B4_3:

Numeric

Approximately what percentage of your customers were located within a radius of 10 km before the flood?

- 999 I don't know
- 997 Not applicable

Q048 - B4_5:**Matrix**

For how long has your company been difficult to reach for the following groups?

	The company has always been accessible for this group	Less than 24 hours difficult to reach	2 to 4 days difficult to reach	5 to 7 days difficult to reach	More than a week difficult to reach	Not applicable
Customers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Suppliers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Employees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q049 - B4_6:**Single coded**

How long has the business been interrupted by the flood?

- 1 Operations have not been interrupted
- 2 Less than 24 hours
- 3 1 to 2 days
- 4 2 to 4 days
- 5 5 to 7 days
- 6 1 to 2 weeks
- 7 2 to 4 weeks
- 8 4 to 6 weeks
- 9 6 to 8 weeks
- 10 More than 2 months
- 999 I don't know

Q295 - B4_8_1:**Numeric**

What was the loss of turnover due to the flooding?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate (in euros)

- 999 I don't know

Ask only if NOT **Q295 - B4_8_1** <= 2000000

Q051 - B4_8_2:

Single coded

Can you perhaps estimate the extent of the loss of turnover due to the flooding?

- 1 Less than €5.000
- 2 Between €5.000 and €9.999
- 3 Between €10.000 and €24.999
- 4 Between €25.000 and €49.999
- 5 Between €50.000 and €99.999
- 6 Between €100.000 and €249.999
- 7 Between €250.000 and €499.999
- 8 Between €500.000 and €999.999
- 9 €1.000.000 or more
- 999 I don't know

DRAFT

Can you indicate which of the following flood protection measures you have taken to protect the company building or other possessions against flood damage?

	Measure taken before or during the flood of July 2021	Measure taken after the flood of July 2021	Planning to take the measure after the July 2021 flood	Measure not taken and not (yet) planning to take	I am not familiar with the measure
Watertight bulkheads	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sandbags in front of the company building	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water pump	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water-resistant floor on the ground floor (e.g. tiles)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water-resistant walls	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other water-resistant building materials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Elevation floor or entrance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Moving to another place of residence with less flood risk	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strengthen foundation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Elevating appliances such as boilers and electricity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Moving valuable possessions to a higher place	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Parking your car or motorcycle in a safe location	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q066 - B6_1:

Single coded

In which sector would you classify the company?

- 1 Agriculture, forestry, fisheries
- 2 Mineral extraction
- 3 Industry
- 4 Energy supply
- 5 Water companies and waste management
- 6 Construction
- 7 Restaurant, café
- 8 Hotel
- 9 Retail
- 10 Private services
- 11 Financial services
- 12 Business services
- 13 Transport and storage
- 14 Information and communication
- 15 Real estate rental and trade
- 16 Public administration and government services
- 17 Education
- 18 Health and welfare care
- 19 Culture, sport and recreation
- 996 Other, ...

Q299 - B6_4_1:

Numeric

Just before the July 2021 flood, how many employees were employed by the company?

If you don't know the exact amount, make an estimate.

999 I don't know

Q072 - B6_6:

Single coded

Does the company own the company building, does the company rent the building?

- 1 The company owns the company building
- 2 The company building is rented

Q073 - B6_7:

Numeric

What is the year of construction of the company building?

Q106 - B6_34_1_1:

Numeric

What was the annual turnover in 2019?

If you are not sure of the exact amount, please make an estimate (in euros).
Your answers will be used for scientific purposes only and will be treated confidentially.

999 I don't know

Ask only if NOT **Q106 - B6_34_1_1** <= 10000000

Q316 - B6_34_1_2:

Single coded

Can you still estimate what the annual turnover was in 2019?

Your answers will be used for scientific purposes only and will be treated confidentially.

- 2 Less than €5.000
- 3 Between €5.000 and €9.999
- 4 Between €10.000 and €24.999
- 5 Between €25.000 and €49.999
- 6 Between €50.000 and €99.999
- 7 Between €100.000 and €149.999
- 8 Between €150.000 and €199.999
- 9 Between €200.000 and €299.999
- 10 Between €300.000 and €399.000
- 11 Between €400.000 and €499.000
- 12 Between €500.000 and €699.999
- 13 Between €700.000 and €999.999
- 14 Between €1.000.000 and €1.499.999
- 15 Between €1.500.000 and €1.999.999
- 16 €2.000.000 or more

Q317 - B6_34_3_1:

Numeric

What was the annual turnover in 2020?

If you are not sure of the exact amount, please make an estimate (in euros).
Your answers will be used for scientific purposes only and will be treated confidentially.

999 I don't know

Ask only if NOT **Q317 - B6_34_3_1** <= 10000000

Q318 - B6_34_3_2:

Single coded

Can you still estimate what the turnover was in 2020?

Uw antwoorden worden enkel voor wetenschappelijke doeleinden gebruikt en worden vertrouwelijk behandeld.

- 2 Less than €5.000
- 3 Between €5.000 and €9.999
- 4 Between €10.000 and €24.999
- 5 Between €25.000 and €49.999
- 6 Between €50.000 and €99.999
- 7 Between €100.000 and €149.999
- 8 Between €150.000 and €199.999
- 9 Between €200.000 and €299.999
- 10 Between €300.000 and €399.000
- 11 Between €400.000 and €499.000
- 12 Between €500.000 and €699.999
- 13 Between €700.000 and €999.999
- 14 Between €1.000.000 and €1.499.999
- 15 Between €1.500.000 and €1.999.999
- 16 €2.000.000 or more

Q110 - B6_35:

Single coded

Finally, we would like to ask you if we can store the company's address with the answers you have given?

- 1 Yes, I give permission to save the address → GO TO END OF QUESTIONNAIRE
- 2 No, I do not give permission to save my address

Ask only if **Q110 - B6_35,2**

Q111 - B6_36:

Single coded

May we store the company's zip code?

- 1 Yes, I give permission to store the company's zip code → GO TO END OF QUESTIONNAIRE
- 2 No, I also do not give permission to save the company's zip code → GO TO END OF QUESTIONNAIRE